

Article

Ensiling of Willow and Poplar Biomass Is Improved by Ensiling Additives

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Abstract: Biomass from willow and poplar harvested for feed during the growing season may be preserved by ensiling; however, little research has focused on ensiling of these biomasses. This study focuses on the use of ensiling additives to reduce the pH to around 4.0 to secure stable storage. Lab-scale ensiling experiments were conducted with different willow and poplar clones, shoot ages, and harvest times (June or September). Ensiling without additives often resulted in limited pH reduction. The pH could be reduced in the biomass of both species by adding formic acid, and the required dose to reduce the pH to 4.0 (buffering capacity, BC) ranged significantly between biomass types but was in the range of 2–5 kg formic acid (78%) per ton fresh weight. BC decreased with increasing dry matter (DM) content and decreasing crude protein content. The pH could also be reduced during ensiling by applying molasses and/or lactic acid bacteria, although not sufficiently in poplar. Willow biomass was ensiled effectively at the pilot scale with less than 7% DM loss by adding formic acid or by mixing with grass biomass. Comparable pH results were obtained at the lab scale and pilot scale. The study demonstrates how willow and poplar can be ensiled; however, more research is needed on quality changes during ensiling.

Keywords: silage; lactic acid bacteria; molasses; formic acid; buffering capacity; pH; Salix; Populus; storage loss

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1. Introduction

Fast-growing tree species such as willow and poplar possess a range of advantages typical of many perennial crops compared to annual crops and which are desirable in relation to the green transition: high biomass yield [1,2], build-up of soil carbon [3–5], low use of pesticides except in the establishment phase [6] and generally low loss of nutrients from the rootzone [5,7].

A specific use of such tree species occurs in free-range pig and poultry production where fast-growing trees may both take up nutrients from nutrient hot-spots in the range area and provide shade and shelter for the animals and, hence providing environmental and animal welfare services [8–11]. There is also increasing interest in the use of trees and agroforestry concepts in relation to grazing ruminants, especially in organic production [12,13].

In addition to environmental and welfare aspects, the produced biomass from willow and poplar may also constitute a potential feed source of supplementary forage [14–18], particularly when harvested as ‘green biomass’ during the growing season, i.e., the harvest of leaves and new shoots. As reviewed by Vandermeulen et al. [19], willow is regarded as a valuable supplement to grass during dry periods for grazing ruminants, providing energy, protein, and micronutrients. Limited research exists on the use of green willow biomass as feed for monogastric livestock. However, its relatively high protein content [17] suggests

that it could serve as a viable alternative to grass clover silage, a well-established amino acid source, particularly for gestating sows, which demonstrate a substantial capacity for roughage intake [20].

Use of tree biomass for feed may also be relevant due to the content of secondary compounds, such as condensed tannins and phenolic glycosides in willow and poplar [14], as well as polyphenols, salicin, and flavonoids in various parts of willow [21,22], including the shoots and leaves [23]. These bioactive compounds may have positive effects on livestock performance [14,24], and the content of tannins in plant biomass used as feed for ruminants may potentially reduce the emission of enteric methane [25] which has been demonstrated specifically for sheep grazing willow [26].

For year-round use of tree biomass for feed, the biomass needs to be preserved to reduce loss of dry matter (DM) and quality during storage. Ensiling is an ideal method for preserving wet biomass and has been used extensively for various types of forage [27].

A few studies have investigated ensiling of willow biomass [16,18,28–30]. Also, a couple of practical guides for low-tech and small-scale ensiling of willow and poplar have been published [31,32], and the experience with ensiling of biomass from browse trees in Africa has been reviewed [33]. Overall, only little research has been conducted on ensiling of green biomass from willow and poplar.

A good ensiling process is characterized by a rapid reduction in pH to a low level, preferably around 4.0, which will protect the biomass from spoilage microorganisms [34]. The fermentation loss is potentially very low but may vary considerably depending on the conditions [35]. The pH reduction during ensiling is driven by conversion of water-soluble carbohydrates (WSCs) to organic acids by lactic acid bacteria (LAB) [35] and, therefore, requires the presence of both WSCs and LAB at sufficient levels. However, the pH reduction during ensiling is also dependent on the buffering capacity (BC) of the biomass, which expresses the resistance of the biomass to pH lowering [36] and which can be defined as the quantity of acid required to reduce the pH to a certain level, e.g., 4.0. Biomasses with high BC, therefore, require higher levels of acids to reduce the pH to the desired level and, consequently, are more dependent on a high concentration of WSCs [36]. Moreover, a high DM content of the biomass may also enhance the ensiling process [36].

The few existing studies on ensiling of green willow biomass indicate a generally low ensilability of the biomass, expressed as a relatively high pH level after ensiling without any additives, e.g., pH levels of 4.7–6.3 [28], 5.8 [16], 5.1 [29] and 4.7–4.9 [18]. It has been suggested that the low ensilability of biomass from willow and other species may be due to the low content of WSCs [16,33].

Ensiling of biomass can be enhanced, e.g., by applying a source of WSCs such as molasses [36] and/or an ensiling additive that can be a biological additive such as an LAB inoculant, or a chemical additive, such as formic acid [37]. Depending on the dose, formic acid can cause direct acidification and suppress spoilage bacteria [37]. Another approach is to mix the poorly ensilable biomass with another crop biomass with a higher content of WSCs as suggested for tree biomass [33]. For instance, forage grasses often have high WSCs concentrations [38] and maize has been co-ensiled with willow [30]. Molasses and LAB have been investigated as additives for ensiling of willow biomass [29]; however, the use of formic acid as a chemical ensiling additive as well as the BC of willow and poplar biomass appear to have not been studied.

Lab-scale ensiling experiments can be performed using e.g., vacuum bags [39] or anaerobic jars [29], and such model systems are convenient for studying the effects of various factors, such as ensiling additives on qualitative silage parameters, including pH. However, for assessment of the mass balance during ensiling, better estimates can be obtained by using larger quantities of biomass, e.g., by ensiling in barrels [29,30].

In this study, we investigated ensiling of different types of green biomass from willow and poplar at the lab-scale as well as the pilot scale for selected treatments. The study consisted of four experiments, with Experiment 1 focusing on the buffering capacity of the biomasses and Experiments 2–4 focusing on ensiling of the biomasses. The main focus was

on the reduction in pH during ensiling as a primary indicator of the ensiling process. The aim of the study was to investigate (i) the buffering capacity of green biomass harvested from willow and poplar during the growing season, (ii) the ensilability of the biomass, (iii) the requirement for and effects of various ensiling additives to reduce the pH of the biomass, and (iv) up-scaling from lab-scale ensiling to pilot-scale ensiling and to explore the feeding value of the ensiled willow. The main hypothesis is that the pH can be reduced significantly during the ensiling of willow and poplar biomass by the appropriate use of ensiling additives.

2. Materials and Methods

2.1. Types of Biomasses Harvested

All biomasses were produced and harvested by the company Ny Vraa (www.nyvraa.dk/en (accessed on 2 September 2024)) near Tylstrup, Denmark (57°10'25.4" N, 9°55'10.5" E) as part of field trials with two or three replicate blocks. Tree biomass was obtained from the willow clones Tordis ((*Salix schwerinii* × *S. viminalis*) × *S. viminalis*) [2] and Clone X (from breeding program, not yet commercially available) and from the poplar clone OP42 (*Populus triochocharpa* × *Populus maximowiczii*) [1]. The willow clone Tordis was established in 2010 on humus soil and had not been fertilized since its establishment. The willow Clone X was established in 2019 on coarse sandy soil and was fertilized with slurry in the establishment year. The poplar clone OP42 was established on coarse sandy soil in 2012 and had not been fertilized since its establishment. All trees had been harvested at least once before harvesting for this study.

Tree biomass was harvested in June and September, i.e., during the growing season, and shoots and leaves were harvested together, typically at a stubble height of 20 cm, which was just above the stool from the previous harvest. For the willow clone Tordis, biomass was harvested at two different 'shoot ages', where '½-year shoots' indicates that the harvested biomass originated solely from growth in the current growth year, i.e., the trees had been harvested in the preceding winter, and '1½-year shoots' originated from both the current and the preceding growth year. For willow Clone X and the poplar clone OP42, only ½-year shoots were harvested. Details on biomass type, shoot age, harvest date, shoot length, and contents of dry matter (DM) and crude protein (CP) in the biomass batches are shown in Table 1, and the table also shows in which of the four experiments (explained in Sections 2.3 and 2.6–2.8) the various biomass batches were used.

In 2021, all tree shoots were harvested using a shrub cutter, whereas shoots harvested in 2022 were harvested by a machine (ZG80, Zero Grazer, Kilnaleck, County Cavan, Ireland), which picks up the biomass directly without chopping the biomass. In both years, the harvested tree shoots were subsequently chopped using a wood-chipper (JF40 Ensiling Machine, JF, Jardim Guarujá, Brazil). The chopper was adjusted to the finest chopping, resulting in a particle size of typically 1–2 cm in length.

In addition to tree biomass, herbaceous biomass was obtained in 2022 from a late first cut in a grass–clover field, dominated by perennial ryegrass and with some red clover and other broadleaved species. This biomass was harvested by machine and chopped as described for tree shoots.

The batches of chopped biomasses were used for the four ensiling experiments which were all initiated on the same day as the harvest. Subsamples were analyzed for DM content on the same day, and other subsamples were frozen for later analysis of CP content and pH.

Table 1. Overview of biomasses used in the four experiments. Shoot age indicates if the harvested biomass originates solely from the current growth year ('½-year shoots') or if it originates from both the current and the preceding growth year ('1½-year shoots'). Mean and standard deviation are given for dry matter (DM) content and crude protein (CP) content, based on either two or three replicate samples.

Biomass Batch No.	Species	Clone	Shoot Age	Previous Harvest	Harvest Date	Shoot Length (m)	DM Content (%)	CP Content (% in DM)	Used in Experiment							
									Exp. 1	Exp. 2	Exp. 3	Exp. 4				
1	Willow	Tordis	½-year shoots	Winter 2020/2021	15 June 2021	1.0	19.3	±0.4	-		x	x				
2					24 June 2021	1.0–1.2	19.9	±0.5	17.5	±1.2					x	
3					9 September 2021	-	33.0	±0.2	-		x					
4					24 September 2021	3.5	37.7	±0.5	8.4	±0.3					x	
5					22 June 2022	-	25.1	±0.2	14.1	-						x
6	Willow	Tordis	1½-year shoots	Winter 2019/2020	15 June 2021	-	36.9	±0.1	-		x					
7					24 June 2021	3.0–3.3	36.9	±0.6	6.2	±0.1				x		
8					9 September 2021	-	41.4	±0.4	-		x					
9					24 September 2021	4.3	43.1	±1.5	6.3	±0.8				x		
10	Willow	Clone X	½-year shoots	Winter 2020/2021	24 June 2021	1.1–1.2	25.1	±0.4	13.6	±0.2			x			
11					9 September 2021	-	35.7	±0.2	-		x					
12					24 September 2021	2.7	40.8	±0.2	4.7	±0.2				x		
13	Poplar	OP42	½-year shoots	Winter 2020/2021	15 June 2021	-	26.4	-	-		x					
14					24 June 2021	0.7–0.8	26.2	±0.3	13.7	±0.5				x		
15					9 September 2021	-	35.0	±0.7	-		x					
16					24 September 2021	2.0–2.5	38.3	±0.5	5.9	±0.6				x		
17	Grass-clover mixture	-	1st cut	-	22 June 2022	-	29.9	±0.3	-					x		
18	Willow + grass		50:50 mix of no. 5 and 17		22 June 2022	-	27.2	±0.1	10.8	-				x		

2.2. Analysis of Dry Matter Content, Crude Protein Content and pH

The dry matter content was analyzed for each biomass batch by drying either two or three replicate subsamples of approx. 150 g at 60 °C until constant weight. The content of N was analyzed for some of the biomass batches (Table 1) by Eurofins Agro Testing, Vejen, Denmark, via Dumas analysis (CEE22, Internal Method Dumas/combustion), with three replicate samples per batch. The CP content was calculated by multiplying the N content by 6.25 [40].

The pH was measured in various samples of fresh and ensiled biomass using the following procedure. Two subsamples of 10 g fresh weight (FW) each were taken from each batch. The samples were either taken directly from unfrozen samples or from frozen samples where the sample material was obtained using a drill. Each sample of 10 g FW was loaded into a PA/PE bag (120 × 250 × 0.09 mm, from LogiCon Nordic, Kolding, Denmark) and 100 g of demineralized water was added. The mixture of biomass and water was massaged initially and after 15 and 30 min, after which the pH was measured in the liquid. The pH was measured with a WTW pH 3310 SET 2 with a SenTix® 41 probe (WTW, Weilheim, Germany), which was calibrated with pH buffer solutions of pH 7.00 and 4.01.

The content of amino acids (Lysine, Methionine, Cystine, and Threonine) in the silage of willow and in the silage of willow + grass was analyzed in accordance with Commission Regulation EC [41], as detailed by Johannsen et al. [42]. The energy content, expressed in Danish Feed Units for sows (FU_{sow}), was analyzed using in vitro enzymatic digestion, as described by Boisen [43]. The feed units were converted to net energy (NE, MJ) according to Theil et al. [44].

2.3. Experiment 1: Dose–Response Experiment for Determination of Buffering Capacity

The buffering capacity (BC) was determined in three types of tree biomass harvested 15 June 2021 and four types harvested 9 September 2021, representing both willow and poplar clones and different shoot ages (biomass batch no. 1, 3, 6, 8, 11, 13, 15, Table 1). BC was determined from a dose–response experiment by the addition of various doses of formic acid and measurement of the subsequent pH, where BC was estimated as the acid dose required to reduce pH to 4.0.

For each biomass type, 14 portions of chopped biomass of 20 g FW were loaded into PA/PE bags (120 × 250 × 0.09 mm) and 5 g of demineralized water was added. For each biomass type, 7 different doses of formic acid (78%) were applied to two replicate bags. The doses corresponded to 0, 0.5, 1, 2, 4, 8 and 12 kg formic acid (78%) per ton FW. After loading the acid into the bags, the bags were massaged to thoroughly mix the biomass, water and acid, and the bags were vacuum packed and stored at 5–10 °C for 20 h (June) or 44 h (September) to allow equilibration between the biomass and the acid. The bags were then opened, 100 g of demineralized water was added to each bag, and the pH was measured as described above.

2.4. General Procedure for Lab-Scale Ensiling Experiments

Lab-scale ensiling experiments were carried out using a vacuum bag system [28,45], using PA/PE bags (LogiCon Nordic, Kolding, Denmark). The general procedure included weighing 750 g FW of the given tree biomass, which was loaded into an inner bag (525 × 600 × 0.090 mm). Depending on the treatment, the ensiling additives were sprayed onto the biomass in the bag using spray bottles with known dose per push and with the additive dose being checked by weighing each bag during application. Afterwards, the biomass was mixed thoroughly with the ensiling additives within the bag, which was then placed into another bag (240 × 650 × 0.150 mm), and this bag was vacuum-packed by a Webomatic vacuum-packing machine (M. Type C 15-HL, M. No. 0310TB1000, Webomatic, Hansastr. 119, D-44866 Bochum, Germany). The silage bags were then stored in an unheated barn (temperature typically in the range of 5–15 °C) for the preplanned duration, after which the bags were frozen at −18 °C until further analysis.

2.5. Ensiling Additives

The additives used in the ensiling experiments included formic acid, molasses and LAB, and all were applied in an aqueous solution to ensure a good distribution on the biomass. For all three additives, the dose of water corresponded to 20 kg water per ton of FW biomass. This addition of water reduced the DM content of the biomass slightly, e.g., with a reduction from 20.0 to 19.6% DM or from 40.0 to 39.2% DM. This reduction in DM content was expected to have little impact on the ensiling process.

Formic acid: Formic acid of 78% concentration was used (Brenntag Nordic, Vejle, Denmark), with a density of 1.18 kg per liter. In the ensiling experiments, the applied dose of formic acid was determined from the analysis of BC, i.e., the required dose of formic acid to reduce the pH to 4.0 for each individual type of biomass (see Section 2.3), typically in the range of 3 to 6 kg formic acid (78%) per ton FW. With a BC of 6 kg per ton FW, for instance, an aqueous solution of formic acid was prepared by dissolving 100 g of formic acid (78%) in 333 g of water. This solution was then applied with a spray bottle at a dose of 19.5 g for a biomass sample of 750 g FW, corresponding to the addition of 4.5 g formic acid (78%) + 15 g water per sample.

Molasses: The applied molasses was standardized sugar beet molasses (Amequ by Dangro flydende melasse, produced by Nordic Sugar, distributed by Amequ and Dangro Nordic A/S, Videbæk, Denmark), with a density of 1.35 kg per liter. According to the declaration, the sucrose content was minimum 43%, the water content was maximum 26%, and the maximum content of microorganisms was 10,000 CFU g⁻¹ for both yeasts and molds and 1000 CFU g⁻¹ for both *Bacillus* species and *Clostridium* species. Based on previous experiments, a standard dose of 20 kg molasses per ton of FW biomass was used, corresponding to at least 8.6 kg sucrose per ton of FW biomass. Molasses was applied in an aqueous solution which was prepared by dissolving 100 g of molasses in 100 g of tap water. Hence, the molasses treatment included the addition of 20 kg molasses + 20 kg water per ton of FW biomass. The solution was applied with a spray bottle at a dose of 30 g for a biomass sample of 750 g FW, resulting in the addition of 15 g molasses + 15 g water per sample.

Lactic acid bacteria: The applied LAB was the product TOPSIL Max ØKO (SH Ensiling, Højslev, Denmark). This is the same product as TOPSIL Max but it uses organic sugar and is, therefore, allowed for use in organic farming in Denmark. The product consists of three homofermentative LAB species:

- *Lactobacillus plantarum* DSMZ 1,6627/1k20749: 75.0 × 10⁹ CFU g⁻¹.
- *Pediococcus acidilactici* NCIMB 3,0005/1k21013: 37.5 × 10⁹ CFU g⁻¹.
- *Lactobacillus paracasei* NCIMB 3,0151/1k20748: 37.5 × 10⁹ CFU g⁻¹.

The total content of LAB is 150 × 10⁹ CFU g⁻¹. The recommended dose is 2 g per ton of FW of maize, grass and alfalfa (typical DM content of 30–35%), and this dose was also applied in these experiments. An aqueous solution was prepared by dissolving 0.5 g of TOPSIL Max ØKO in 5 kg of cold water. This solution was applied with a spray bottle at a dose of 15 g for a biomass sample of 750 g FW, resulting in the addition of 0.0015 g TOPSIL + 15 g water per sample.

2.6. Experiment 2, Lab-Scale-Ensiling: Development of pH in Willow Silage over Time

A lab-scale experiment was performed to study the development of pH in willow biomass during ensiling with or without ensiling additives. A series of 32 silage bags were prepared with willow biomass from ½-year shoots from the clone Tordis, harvested 15 June 2021 with a DM content of 19.3% (biomass batch no. 1, Table 1). Sixteen bags were prepared without any ensiling additives, and 16 bags were prepared with a combination of molasses (20 kg per ton FW) and LAB TOPSIL Max Øko (2 g per ton FW). Both molasses and LAB were applied as aqueous solutions, corresponding to the addition of 40 kg water per ton FW. The biomass was vacuum packed within 8 h from harvest. Two replicate bags of each

of the two additive treatments were frozen after the following ensiling durations: 0, 1, 2, 5, 10, 20, 48 and 85 days. Samples were later used for analysis of pH.

2.7. Experiment 3, Lab-Scale Ensiling: Effects of Additives on Ensiling of Willow and Poplar Harvested in June or September

A lab-scale experiment was performed to study the effect of different ensiling additives on ensiling of four types of green tree biomass harvested in June or September 2021. The experiment included four factors: biomass type (4 levels), harvest time (2 levels), ensiling additive (5 levels) and ensiling duration (2 levels, with or without ensiling). The four biomass types represented both willow and poplar clones, different shoot ages, biomass harvested 24 June or 24 September 2021. The DM content ranged from 19.9 to 43.1% (biomass batch no. 2, 4, 7, 9, 10, 12, 14, 16, Table 1).

For each of the four biomass types and two harvest times, five different additive treatments were applied, as described in Table 2. The treatments included a control without additive and the addition of either formic acid, molasses, LAB, or molasses + LAB. The dose of formic acid (78%) was determined from the analysis of BC within two weeks prior to the ensiling experiment (see Section 2.3) and ranged between 2.6 and 6.0 kg per ton FW (Table 2). The doses of molasses and LAB were based on previous experiences and recommendations, respectively. All additives were applied as aqueous solutions, and a total of either 20 or 40 kg water was added per ton FW (Table 2).

Table 2. Overview of additive treatments to the four biomass types and the two harvest dates in ensiling Experiment 3.

Species	Clone	Shoot Age	Harvest Date	Treatment No. and Ensiling Additive				
				1. Untreated	2. Formic Acid	3. Molasses	4. Lactic Acid Bacteria	5. Molasses + Lactic Acid Bacteria
				Dose				
				-	kg 78% Acid + kg Water per ton FW	kg Molasses + kg Water per ton FW	g Topsil Max ØKO + kg Water per ton FW	kg Molasses + g Topsil Max ØKO + kg Water per ton FW
Willow	Tordis	½-year shoots	24 June 2021	-	6.0 kg + 20 kg	20 kg + 20 kg	2 g + 20 kg	20 kg + 2 g + 40 kg
			24 September 2021	-	3.0 kg + 20 kg	20 kg + 20 kg	2 g + 20 kg	20 kg + 2 g + 40 kg
Willow	Tordis	1½-year shoots	24 June 2021	-	3.0 kg + 20 kg	20 kg + 20 kg	2 g + 20 kg	20 kg + 2 g + 40 kg
			24 September 2021	-	2.6 kg + 20 kg	20 kg + 20 kg	2 g + 20 kg	20 kg + 2 g + 40 kg
Willow	Clone X	½-year shoots	24 June 2021	-	6.0 kg + 20 kg	20 kg + 20 kg	2 g + 20 kg	20 kg + 2 g + 40 kg
			24 September 2021	-	5.0 kg + 20 kg	20 kg + 20 kg	2 g + 20 kg	20 kg + 2 g + 40 kg
Poplar	OP42	½-year shoots	24 June 2021	-	5.0 kg + 20 kg	20 kg + 20 kg	2 g + 20 kg	20 kg + 2 g + 40 kg
			24 September 2021	-	2.6 kg + 20 kg	20 kg + 20 kg	2 g + 20 kg	20 kg + 2 g + 40 kg

For each combination of biomass type, harvest time, and additive treatment, three replicate vacuum bags were prepared with 750 g FW, resulting in a total of 120 bags. The bags were vacuum packed within 10 h from harvest of the biomass. One replicate bag was frozen at -18°C within 12 h after vacuum packing, corresponding to an unensiled control (0 days of ensiling). The other two replicate bags (vacuum packed with two layers of 0.150 mm PA/PE, i.e., first vacuum-packing in one bag and then in another bag) were stored for ensiling for 75 days at ambient temperature in an unheated barn. The pH was measured as described above in duplicate subsamples from the unensiled bag and from the two ensiled bags per combination.

2.8. Experiment 4, Lab-Scale and Pilot-Scale Ensiling: Ensiling of Willow and Willow + Grass Mixture

Based on results from Experiments 2 and 3 in 2021, a combined lab-scale and pilot-scale experiment was initiated in 2022. The aim was to test upscaling of the ensiling procedure for willow with formic acid and to test grass as an ‘ensiling additive’ in mixture with willow to improve the ensiling of willow biomass. Also, the aim was to estimate mass loss during ensiling at the pilot scale.

The tree biomass represented ½-year shoots of the willow clone Tordis with a DM content of 25.1% (biomass batch no. 5, Table 1), which was ensiled with the addition of 5 kg formic acid (78%) per ton FW. In addition, willow biomass was co-ensiled with grass–clover biomass (biomass batch no. 17) in a ratio of approx. 50:50 % FW basis, resulting in a willow + grass mixture with 27.2% DM (biomass batch no. 18).

Both biomasses were harvested 22 June 2022 and chopped. Formic acid was applied to willow biomass as an aqueous solution of 15.6% formic acid applied at a dose of 25 kg per ton FW. Approx. 180 kg FW of chopped willow was distributed in a 15 cm layer on a concrete floor, and formic acid solution was sprayed onto the biomass using a garden sprayer. The biomass was turned and mixed during spraying to obtain a uniform distribution. The mixture of willow + grass was obtained by weighing 80 kg FW of each biomass and mixing thoroughly by turning on a concrete floor.

Both willow biomasses with formic acid and willow + grass were loaded into two 60 L open top barrels (Plastic Blue UN Approved Open Top Drum in HDPE). The biomass was continuously compressed during filling of the barrels by a person trampling on the biomass layer by layer. The barrels were filled and closed with as much biomass as possible to diminish the air content. After filling, the barrels were weighed to determine the initial biomass weight. The barrels were stored in an unheated barn for 257 days to mimic long-term storage for year-round supply, then weighed to determine the final biomass weight, and opened for visual evaluation. Biomass samples were taken before ensiling and after ensiling (at 10–15 cm distance from the surface after opening the barrels) for duplicate analysis of DM content and pH as described above.

In addition to pilot-scale ensiling, lab-scale ensiling was performed by vacuum packing four bags of approx. 700 g of willow biomass with formic acid and four bags with willow + grass, and the bags were stored together with the barrels and opened after 257 days of ensiling for duplicate analysis of pH. In addition, samples of fresh frozen willow biomass without and with formic acid and willow + grass was analyzed for pH as unensiled references.

2.9. Data Analyses

2.9.1. Experiment 1

The BC of willow and poplar biomasses was estimated individually for the different types of tree biomass and the two harvest times (Table 1), and both on a FW and a DM basis by fitting the relationship between the dose of formic acid and pH by Equation (1):

$$y = a + b \times e^{(-c \times x)} \quad (1)$$

where y is the pH value, x is the dose of 78% formic acid (kg ton^{-1} FW or DM), a is the lower asymptote for pH at infinitely high doses, b is the difference between the lower asymptote and the intercept with the y axis, and c is a constant expressing the rate at which pH decreases with increasing dose. The relationship was fitted with SAS software release 9.3 [46] using the proc nlmixed procedure, and estimates and 95% confidence limits were calculated for pH without formic acid addition, and the required formic acid dose to reduce the pH to 4.0, which corresponds to BC, was calculated by rewriting Equation (1) as Equation (2):

$$x = \ln((y - a)/b) - c \quad (2)$$

Significant differences in estimates of BC were evaluated from the 95% confidence limits.

The relationships between measured DM and estimated BC and between measured CP (% of DM) and estimated BC were analyzed by linear regression, with separate analyses for BC on FW and DM basis. In both models, the response variable was BC, and the explanatory variables were either DM (%) or CP (% in DM). The analyses were performed with R software version 4.1.3 using the function `lm`.

2.9.2. Experiment 2

The data for pH development in willow silage over time were analyzed with R software, both as analysis of variance and non-linear regression. The analysis of variance was performed using a model that included treatment (class variable, with or without ensiling additives), ensiling duration (class variable, 0, 1, 5, 10, 20, 48 and 85 days) and their interacting effects, as well as replicate vacuum bags (class variable, two bags per combination of treatment and ensiling duration). The mean value of the two replicate pH measurements per vacuum bag was used in the analysis. A total of 64 observations were included. The analysis was carried out using the R functions `lm` and `anova`. The functions `emmeans` and `multcomp` were used to estimate the expected means and LSD groups (compact letter display).

The non-linear regression analysis was performed separately for the treatments without and with ensiling additive using a three-parameter model, as described in Equation (1), where y is the pH value, x is the ensiling duration (numerical variable), and a , b , and c are parameters. The analysis was performed using the `nlme` package in R and the `nls` function.

2.9.3. Experiment 3

The data for pH before and after ensiling of different types and harvest times of tree biomass with different additive treatments were all analyzed in one analysis using the `optimx` package in R software version 4.1.3., with pH as the response variable and with four explanatory variables, all as class variables: biomass type (4 levels), harvest time (2 levels), ensiling additive (5 levels) and ensiling duration (with or without ensiling). All possible interactions between the main factors were included in the model, and the model was not reduced, since all interactions were significant. The two replicate silage bags per combination of biomass type \times harvest time \times ensiling additive were included as the random effect. The model fit was evaluated by plotting residuals versus predicted values. LSD groups were calculated within each combination of biomass type and harvest time, i.e., for comparison of the effects of ensiling additives and ensiling duration.

2.9.4. Experiment 4

The pH data from the lab-scale and pilot-scale experiment were analyzed together using the `lmer` function of the `lm4` package in R software version 2022.07.2 Build 576. The model included pH as the response variable and a treatment factor with seven treatments: (1) willow fresh frozen without formic acid, (2) willow fresh frozen with formic acid, (3) willow ensiled with formic acid in vacuum bags, (4) willow ensiled with formic acid in barrels, (5) willow + grass fresh frozen, (6) willow + grass ensiled in vacuum bags and (7) willow + grass ensiled in barrels. The two replicate vacuum bags and two replicate barrels within each biomass type were included as the random effect. The distribution of the data was tested using the Shapiro–Wilk test and the data fit was evaluated from a residual plot. Estimates of expected marginal means and compact letter display were calculated using the `em_res` function.

FW and DM mass losses during ensiling in barrels were calculated based on the initial and final weight and initial and final DM content of the biomass in each barrel. Mean and standard deviation were calculated across two barrels per biomass type.

3. Results

3.1. Buffering Capacity in Willow and Poplar Harvested in June or September

The relationships between the dose of formic acid and the response pH for various types of biomasses are shown in Figure 1 along with the estimates of BC, and in general, the observed relationship was described well by the function. The estimated BC required to reduce the pH to 4.0 varied between 2.5 and 4.8 kg formic acid per ton FW and between 6.1 and 24.9 kg per ton DM. For ½-year shoots of willow clone Tordis and poplar clone OP42, BC was significantly lower in September than in June, with reductions of 58 and 34% on a FW basis, respectively, and 75 and 50% on a DM basis, respectively. BC was not estimated for willow Clone X in June, but in September BC was significantly higher for ½-year shoots of Clone X than for ½-year shoots of Tordis, demonstrating that differences in BC may occur between willow clones. For 1½-year shoots of the willow clone Tordis, BC was relatively low in both June and September, with no significant difference between the two harvest times.

Figure 1. Cont.

Figure 1. Dose–response relationship between added formic acid and pH in biomass from willow and poplar clones, harvested either (A,C,E,G) 15 June 2021 or (B,D,F,H) or 9 September 2021. Figures show relationships on (A–D) a fresh weight (FW) basis and (E–H) a dry weight (DW) basis, respectively. Shoots were either ½-year shoots or 1½-year shoots, see Table 1 for details. Symbols indicate measured values (with two replicates per dose and biomass type), and lines indicate the predicted relationship. The horizontal line indicates pH 4.0. The estimated dose to achieve pH 4.0 and 95% confidence limits are given for each biomass type, corresponding to the buffering capacity.

When analyzing across biomass types, shoot ages, and harvest times, BC was negatively correlated with DM content and positively correlated with CP content (Figure 2). However, the effect was only significant for BC calculated on a DM basis. Hence, the predicted BC decreased significantly ($p = 0.006$) from 22.1 to 5.3 kg formic acid (78%) per ton DM, when the DM content of the biomass increased from 20 to 40% (Figure 2A). Likewise, BC increased significantly ($p = 0.012$) from 6.7 to 19.2 kg formic acid per ton DM when the CP content increased from 5 to 15% (Figure 2B).

Figure 2. Relationship between (A) dry matter (DM) content and buffering capacity (BC) and (B) crude protein (CP) content and BC in tree biomass. BC is estimated both on a fresh weight (FW) and a DM basis. The tree biomass covers different clones and shoot ages of willow and poplar harvested in either June or September 2021. Note that CP was analyzed in biomass that was harvested 9–15 days later than the biomass used for the analysis of BC. See Table 1 for details. Symbols indicate the measured values of DM and CP and the estimated value of BC based on dose–response relationships in Figure 1. The full and dashed lines indicate significant and non-significant linear relationship, respectively.

3.2. Development of pH in Willow Silage over Time

The development of pH in willow silage over 85 days with and without ensiling additives in ensiling Experiment 2 is shown in Figure 3. The fitted non-linear functions clearly illustrate that the pH stabilized within a few days but at a much lower level when applying molasses + LAB compared to no additive application. In the analysis of variance, there was highly significant effect of both additive treatment, ensiling duration, and their interacting effects ($p < 0.001$ for all). For biomass ensiled without additives, the pH decreased within the first 5–10 days and stabilized at a level of around 5.18–5.50. For biomass ensiled with molasses and LAB, the pH decreased more rapidly and to a lower level, and the pH was reduced to 4.19 after 5 days of ensiling. There was a further slight decline in the pH to 4.10 after 90 days, but there were no significant differences between ensiling durations from 5 to 90 days, indicating that the pH stabilized within 5 days. When comparing the two ensiling additive treatments within each ensiling duration, the treatment with ensiling additives resulted in a significantly lower pH compared to no additive for all ensiling durations from 2 days up to 90 days.

Figure 3. Development of pH during ensiling of biomass from ½-year shoots of the willow clone Tordis in ensiling Experiment 2, harvested 15 June 2021. Ensiling was performed either without any additives or with the addition of a combination of sugar beet molasses and lactic acid bacteria (LAB). Symbols and error bars represent the mean value and standard deviation of two pH measurements in each of two individual vacuum bags. Letters indicate significant differences; values within additive treatments followed by the same letter are not significantly different ($p = 0.05$). Lines indicate the predicted non-linear relationship.

3.3. Effects of Additives on Ensiling of Willow and Poplar Harvested in June or September

The effects of biomass type, harvest time, ensiling additives, and ensiling duration on pH in Experiment 3 are shown in Figure 4. There were significant effects of all main factors as well as all their interactions on pH ($p < 0.001$ for all).

In general, there was only a limited reduction in pH during ensiling of both willow and poplar when no ensiling additive was applied ('untreated'). This was very pronounced for biomass harvested in September (Figure 4B,D,F,H) with only a significant but small reduction in pH for poplar OP42 biomass (Figure 4H). For biomass harvested in June, the pH was significantly reduced for all four biomass types (Figure 4A,C,E,G), but the reduction was very small in willow Tordis biomass from ½-year shoots (Figure 4A) and moderate in poplar OP42 biomass (Figure 4G).

The addition of formic acid reduced the pH immediately after application, and since the acid dose was adjusted specifically to each biomass type and harvest time, it is not surprising that the pH was relatively close to pH 4.0 for unensiled biomass, except for poplar OP42 biomass harvested in September, where the applied acid dose appeared to have been too low (Figure 4H). Moreover, the pH remained at the same level or slightly lower after 75 days of ensiling for all combinations of biomass type and harvest time.

Figure 4. pH in willow and poplar biomass before and after ensiling for 75 days in ensiling Experiment 3. Biomass from the willow clones (A–D) Tordis and (E,F) Clone X and (G,H) the poplar clone OP42 was harvested either (A,C,E,G) 24 June 2021 or (B,D,F,H) 24 September 2021. The biomass was harvested from plants that had previously been harvested during the winter 2020/2021 (½-year shoots) or during the winter 2019/2020 (1½-year shoots), see Table 1 for details. The biomass was ensiled either without any additives (untreated) or with formic acid, molasses, lactic acid bacteria (LAB) or molasses + LAB, see Table 2 for details. The formic acid dose was adjusted specifically to each biomass type to obtain an initial pH of approx. 4.0. Columns and error bars indicate the mean and standard deviation of two replicate samples from one silage bag for unensiled biomass and from two silage bags for ensiled biomass. Letters indicate LSD groups; within each figure, columns with the same letter are not significantly different.

As an alternative to chemical ensiling, the application of molasses and/or LAB for biological ensiling also resulted in a significant reduction in pH compared to untreated ensiled biomass for most combinations of willow biomass type and harvest time (Figure 4A–F), except for the biomass from ½-year shoots of Clone X harvested in June, where the pH was at a relatively low level after ensiling of untreated biomass (Figure 4E).

For poplar, there was either little or no significant effect on pH of applying molasses and/or LAB compared to the untreated, ensiled biomass (Figure 4G,H), and the pH was only reduced to a pH level in the range 4.6–5.0 after biological ensiling of poplar biomass.

3.4. Ensiling of Willow and Willow + Grass Mixture at Pilot-Scale

When opening the barrels after 257 days of ensiling in Experiment 4, there was considerable occurrence of mold on the surface and to approx. 5–8 cm depth of the willow silage but only little mold on the surface of the willow + grass silage. From a subjective evaluation, the silage in all four barrels smelled fresh and good, with willow + grass silage smelling more aromatic than pure willow silage. The willow silage and willow + grass silage in the vacuum bags also smelled fresh and good; however, the color of the silage appeared slightly darker compared to the silage in the barrels.

The pH differed significantly between the seven biomasses/treatments ($p < 0.001$), and the mean values are shown in Figure 5. For fresh willow, the pH was reduced from 6.22 to 4.35 when adding 5 kg of formic acid (78%) per ton FW. After ensiling, the pH was reduced to around 4.2 in willow silage, both in bags and in barrels. Hence, the addition of formic acid may have enhanced subsequent fermentation and further pH reduction in willow biomass.

Figure 5. pH in willow and willow + grass before and after ensiling in either vacuum bags or 60 L barrels for 257 days in ensiling Experiment 4, harvested 22 June 2022. For pure willow, formic acid was added as an ensiling additive at a dose of 5 kg (78%) per ton fresh weight. For fresh frozen willow biomass, pH was measured both before and after addition of formic acid. Columns indicate the mean value; for fresh frozen biomass, the columns represent two replicate samples, and for ensiled biomass, the columns represent two replicate samples from each of two vacuum bags or two barrels. Letters indicate LSD groups; columns with the same letter are not significantly different. Error bars indicate the 95% confidence limits as calculated in the analysis of variance.

For willow + grass, the pH was reduced from 6.18 in fresh biomass to 4.02–4.03 in silage. There was no significant difference in pH between ensiling in vacuum bags and ensiling in barrels, neither in willow nor in willow + grass (Figure 5).

The initial density and initial and final DM content and biomass weight in the barrels are shown in Table 3. On a FW basis, there were only minor mass losses of 0.3 and 1.2% during ensiling of willow and willow + grass, respectively. However, due to a slight

reduction in DM content in the biomass, there were DM losses of 6.5 and 6.7%, respectively (Table 3).

Table 3. Mass balance for ensiling of willow and willow + grass at pilot-scale in ensiling Experiment 4, harvested 22 June 2022. Silage samples were taken before and after 257 days of ensiling to obtain initial and final values and mean and standard deviation were calculated across two barrels per biomass type.

Parameter	Time	Willow Mean ± Std.dev.	Willow + Grass Mean ± Std.dev.
Density, kg FM m ⁻³	Initial	605 ± 14	547 ± 1
DM content, %	Initial	24.9 ± 0.27	27.1 ± 0.04
	Final	23.2 ± 0.00	25.6 ± 0.10
CP content, %	Initial	14.1 ¹	10.8 ¹
	Final	13.6 ± 0.5	11.6 ± 0.0
Biomass fresh weight, kg FW	Initial	36.3 ± 0.8	32.8 ± 0.1
	Final	36.2 ± 0.9	32.5 ± 0.1
Biomass dry weight, kg DM	Initial	9.0 ± 0.2	8.9 ± 0.02
	Final	8.4 ± 0.2	8.3 ± 0.03
FW mass loss, % of initial weight	-	0.3 ± 0.3	1.2 ± 0.1
DM mass loss, % of initial weight	-	6.5 ± 0.8	6.7 ± 0.1

¹ Only one observation per biomass type.

For both the fresh and ensiled biomasses, the CP content was numerically higher in willow than in the mixture of willow and grass (Table 4). The ensiling process reduced the CP content in willow by 4% and increased the CP content in the willow + grass biomasses by 7%. The energy content decreased in the ensiled biomasses compared to their fresh counterparts, by approximately 37% for willow and 27% for willow + grass. The in vitro organic matter digestibility (EDOM and EDOMi) of the ensiled biomasses similarly decreased by 19% to 31% compared to that of the fresh biomasses.

Table 4. Analysis of feed value of freshly harvested willow and willow + grass harvested on 22 June 2022 and ensiled willow and willow + grass sampled from barrels on 6 March 2023. For fresh biomass, values are based on one sample per biomass type. For silage, the mean and standard deviation is based on two samples per biomass type, except analyses of amino acids, which were based on one sample per type.

Parameter	Unit	Fresh Willow	Fresh Willow + Grass	Silage of Willow	Silage of Willow + Grass
		Mean	Mean	Mean Std. dev.	Mean Std. dev.
DM	%	24.6	27.1	23.2 ± 0.0	25.6 ± 0.1
Crude ash	% in DM	7.7	6.9	7.9 ± 0.7	7.6 ± 0.2
Fat	% in DM	2.1	2	1.9 ± 0.1	2.4 ± 0.2
CP	% in DM	14.1	10.8	13.6 ± 0.5	11.6 ± 0.0
NE ¹	FUsow ² /kg DM	0.35	0.45	0.22 ± 0.03	0.33 ± 0.02
NE ¹	MJ/kg DM	2.70	3.48	1.71 ± 0.20	2.56 ± 0.13
EDOM ³	%	38.2	43.0	30.4 ± 0.5	34.7 ± 1.0
EDOMi ⁴	%	26.9	33.7	18.7 ± 2.2	26.1 ± 0.7
<i>Amino acids</i>					
Lysine	g/kg DM	-	-	9.2	5.3
Methionine	g/kg DM	-	-	3.0	1.8
Cysteine + Cystine	g/kg DM	-	-	1.4	0.8
Threonine	g/kg DM	-	-	6.8	4.3

¹ Net energy (NE). ² Danish Feed Units for sows corresponding to 7.7 MJ [43,44]. ³ Enzyme digestible organic matter. ⁴ Enzyme digestible organic matter at ileal level.

4. Discussion

4.1. Buffering Capacity in Willow and Poplar Harvested in June and September

The results from Experiment 1 in 2021 show that the required dose of formic acid (78%) for reducing the pH in the willow and poplar biomass is generally in the range of 2–5 kg per ton FW, corresponding to 6–25 kg per ton DW (Figure 1). However, both the harvest time and shoot age may affect the BC of tree biomass; the BC appears to decrease from June to September for the ½-year shoots, whereas the BC for the 1½-year shoots is low already in June. For comparison, the BC for wheat and barley straw has been estimated to be 9.9 and 20.3 kg formic acid per kg DM [45].

The BC appears to be negatively correlated with the DM content and positively correlated with the CP content in the tree biomass (Figure 2). It should be mentioned that the DM and CP content in the biomass are confounded, and from the present data, the causality of these two factors cannot be determined. The BC of herbage biomass has been found to be mainly related to the anion fraction of the plant material, whereas proteins contributed to a lesser extent [47]. Therefore, the variation in the BC in the tree biomass may partly be related to the CP content but also to other constituents which were not analyzed.

It must also be noted that the CP content was analyzed in the biomass that was harvested 9 or 15 days later than the biomass used for the BC analysis (see Table 1), and the CP may have changed slightly during this period. Nevertheless, the predicted relationship between the DM content and BC provides a practical and useful indication of the required dose of formic acid to apply to reduce the pH to 4.0 in willow or poplar biomass, given that the DM content is known.

In the pilot-scale ensiling of willow in June 2022 in Experiment 4, a dose of 5 kg of formic acid was applied, based on the results obtained in June 2021. The pH results from Experiment 4 indicate that a higher acid dose may have been required for the biomass harvested in June 2022 (Figure 5), and this illustrates that some variation in the BC may occur also between biomasses even of the same cultivar and shoot age.

4.2. Ensiling of Willow and Poplar without Ensiling Additives

The results from Experiment 2 and Experiment 3 clearly show that the willow biomass harvested in June or September ensiled poorly without any additives, whereas the addition of molasses + LAB enhanced the ensiling process, both in terms of the more rapid pH decrease (Figure 3) and the pH reduction to a lower final level (Figures 3 and 4). The poor ensilability of the willow harvested during the growing season is consistent with previous studies of ensiling biomass from ½-year-old willow shoots without additives, which also resulted in a high pH [16,18,28,29]. Our results are somehow in contrast to those from the study by Larsen et al. [28], which indicated a poorer ensilability of willow when harvesting in June–July compared to harvesting in August or September. There seems to be very little knowledge on the ensilability of poplar; however, a study reported a relatively low pH of 4.2 in willow silage and a higher pH of 4.6 in poplar silage [48].

Our results and previous studies strongly suggest that there is often a need for the application of ensiling additives to green willow and poplar biomass to ensure a good ensiling process with a sufficiently low pH in the range of 4.0, and the need seems to be more pronounced when harvesting biomass in September rather than in June.

4.3. Effect of Additives on Ensiling of Willow and Poplar

The results from Experiment 3 demonstrate that chemical ensiling by the application of formic acid in the appropriate dose can ensure a low and stable pH during the ensiling of both willow and poplar biomass (Figure 4). Formic acid is frequently used as an ensiling additive due to its low production costs and high acidification capacity [49].

The addition of molasses and LAB also had a significant effect on the pH reduction during the ensiling of willow (Figure 4). Interestingly, the separate addition of molasses and LAB had very similar effects on the pH after ensiling, with no significant differences in the pH between these two treatments in six of the eight combinations of biomass and

harvest time (all except Figure 4B,H). Also, there seems to be a very small additive effect of applying a combination of molasses and LAB compared to molasses or LAB alone, since the combination only reduced the pH slightly more and only significantly for the biomass of ½-year-old shoots of the willow clone Tordis (Figure 4A). Therefore, ensiling willow biomass may be enhanced by either applying molasses or LAB, whereas the combined treatment only provides little extra effect. For comparison, Muklada et al. [29] found that LAB significantly reduced the pH to 4.2 when ensiling willow biomass, whereas molasses had no significant effect (pH 4.9) compared to with no additive (pH 5.1). The lacking effect of molasses in their study may have been due to a relatively high concentration of WSCs of 107 g kg⁻¹ DM, which is much higher than the 35 g kg⁻¹ DM reported by Smith et al. [16]. Heubeck [30] reported a concentration of WSCs of 122 g kg⁻¹ DM in willow biomass; however, the pH in the resulting silage was not reported. Unfortunately, WSCs in the biomasses were not analyzed in our study.

Since the addition of molasses and LAB to the poplar biomass did not decrease or only slightly decreased the pH further compared to no treatment (Figure 4G,H), the ensiling process in poplar OP42 biomass may be inhibited by other factors and, hence, chemical ensiling with formic acid may be more relevant for this type of biomass.

Overall, the results show that there is often a need for applying ensiling additives to achieve a good ensiling process with a low pH when ensiling the green biomass of willow and poplar. For willow, similar effects on the pH can be obtained by applying an appropriate dose of formic acid or by applying either molasses or LAB, and additional benefit seems to be obtained only occasionally by applying a combination of molasses and LAB. For poplar, there seems to be little effect of molasses and LAB on the pH, and the application of formic acid appears to be the most relevant ensiling additive for poplar biomass.

4.4. *Ensiling of Willow and Willow + Grass Mixture on Pilot Scale*

The occurrence of mold primarily in the barrels with the silage of willow in Experiment 4 indicates that the ingress of some oxygen was enabled between the barrel and the lid. However, it also shows that the pure willow silage is more vulnerable to secondary fermentation than the willow + grass silage, and this risk needs consideration when ensiling willow commercially, not least the risk of quality loss during feed-out from a silage silo. Heubeck [30] also reported the occurrence of mold in the upper 10 cm layer when ensiling willow in barrels but concluded that “this problem does not occur at field scale, where flexible plastic covers allow fermentation gases to escape from the silage stack, while generally excluding oxygen from the silage”.

The pH dropped to a low level during the ensiling of willow + grass (Figure 5), which demonstrates that the grass can serve as an ensiling additive when mixed with the willow biomass and ensure a sufficiently low pH for good preservation of the biomass mixture. The positive effect of grass may be due to a higher content of WSCs, which is often observed in grass species [38].

Since there was no difference in the pH between the biomass ensiled in vacuum bags and barrels (Figure 5), the ensiling process appears to be comparable on these two scales and, therefore, ensiling in vacuum bags can serve to mimic ensiling on a larger scale. Hence, our results support those from previous studies showing that ensiling in vacuum bags can serve as a realistic model system for studying the effects of various factors on ensiling [39].

The DM loss of 6.5–6.7% during the ensiling of willow and willow + grass on the pilot scale (Table 3) is slightly higher than the DM loss 2.4–3.3% found during the pilot-scale ensiling of grass pulp after the extraction of protein-rich juice from grass [50]. The DM loss during ensiling may partly be due to the reduction in the FW mass and partly due to the reduction in the DM content (Table 3). Hatt and Clauss [32] also reported a slight reduction in the DM content from 47.8 to 46.8% after ensiling the biomass of willow and other tree species; however, DM mass loss was not reported.

4.5. Feeding Value

Identifying local protein sources to reduce the dependence on imported soybeans is a key objective in livestock production. Willow silage has been recognized as a potential source of crude protein (CP), with reported CP levels of 18% in DM, and up to 22% in DM in silage made from leaves only [16]. These values are significantly higher than the CP content observed in ensiled willow and willow + grass (11.6–13.6% of DM) in the current study (Table 4). As the ensiling process had minimal effect on the CP content, in accordance with earlier studies [16,24], no clear explanation exists for the relatively low CP levels in the willow silage tested. From a pig nutritional standpoint, the high lysine and methionine levels in the willow silage (Table 4) are advantageous and comparable to, or even exceed, those found in fresh and ensiled grass-clover [20]. Nevertheless, the potential of ensiled willow biomass to provide energy for pigs appears to be low, with substantially lower net energy levels (0.22 to 0.33 FUsow/kg DM) compared to those of ensiled grass-clover (0.65 FUsow/kg DM) [42].

4.6. Practical Perspectives and Future Research

Overall, the ensiling experiments demonstrate that it is possible to preserve green willow and poplar biomass effectively by ensiling, provided an appropriate ensiling additive is applied that can ensure rapid and sufficient pH reduction and minimize DM loss. A low pH is generally a good indicator of a successful ensiling process, and the pH reduction facilitated by ensiling additives is generally expected to improve the preservation of the feed quality when ensiling willow biomass. Future research should investigate the potential changes in qualitative parameters during the ensiling of tree biomass, including the production of different volatile fatty acids, which may affect the palatability of the silage. Also, it is important to consider what the willow silage is to be used for, since quality requirements may differ between different applications. For instance, the tree silage may be used as (1) possible supplementary forage for large and small ruminants [14,16,18,24,26], or (2) with the specific purpose of reducing enteric methane production from ruminants in general [25,26] or (3) even as feed for browsing ungulates such as giraffes in zoos [33]. The pilot testing of the pig nutritional value of willow biomass in this study indicates its low energy content and low organic matter digestibility. These outcomes could potentially be improved by ensiling only willow leaves to reduce the fiber content from the shoots or by harvesting at earlier stages of maturity. Future research should investigate the potential for improving the pig nutritional value while transferring bioactive compounds from the willow to sow milk, and thereby support piglet health.

Our study does not reveal the mechanisms restricting the ensiling of willow and poplar biomass without additives. Further investigations are required to illuminate and distinguish between the potential effects of a low DM content, a low content of WSCs, and high BC as well as other potentially inhibitory factors for the ensiling process. For example, it is relevant to analyze the content of WSCs in various types of tree biomass. Nevertheless, this study provides valuable knowledge in a poorly studied area; it documents a frequently occurring need for the application of additives when ensiling willow and poplar biomass, and it provides practically applicable knowledge regarding the choice of ensiling additive as well as guidelines for the required dose of formic acid.

5. Conclusions

This study is concerned with preserving green tree biomass harvested from willow and poplar during the growing season by ensiling, i.e., by reducing the pH to a low level around 4.0. The lab-scale ensiling experiments demonstrate that pH is often not reduced sufficiently in willow and poplar biomass during ensiling without applying an ensiling additive. However, a low pH level can be obtained in willow biomass either by applying a dose of 2–5 kg per ton FW of formic acid (78%) or by adding molasses and/or LAB, which can ensure a rapid and adequate pH reduction. For poplar biomass, molasses and LAB seem less effective, and formic acid appears to be more suitable as an ensiling additive.

The buffering capacity of tree biomass, defined as the required dose of formic acid to reduce the pH to 4.0, differed between biomass types and harvest dates but typically ranged between 2 and 5 kg formic acid (78%) per ton FW. The buffering capacity decreased with increasing DM content of the biomass.

The pilot-scale experiment demonstrates that comparable pH results can be obtained when ensiling at the lab-scale in vacuum bags as when ensiling at the pilot-scale in 60 L barrels. The experiment also showed that willow biomass can be ensiled either by the application of formic acid or by mixing with grass biomass, with a mass loss of 6–7%.

Overall, the study provides guidelines for how to ensure a low pH during ensiling of willow and poplar biomass. Further research is needed to investigate the mechanisms involved in the ensiling process as well as the effect of ensiling on silage quality parameters.

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